

S₅: piece of cake, almost

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In a previous article [1] the 24-element symmetric group S_4 was derived quickly using Kronecker evolution and column-swapping. Although S_5 cannot have Kronecker parents – 5 is prime - spawning was still accomplished by the same swapping operations.

This time the parent matrices are the circulants U1 and U2:

$$U1 = \begin{pmatrix} 12345 \\ 23451 \\ 34512 \\ 45123 \\ 51234 \end{pmatrix} \quad U2 = \begin{pmatrix} 54321 \\ 43215 \\ 32154 \\ 21543 \\ 15432 \end{pmatrix}$$

These two matrices generated the entire 120 elements of S_5 ; their tag-stream is plotted below, showing as usual a step-wise behavior.

Now, to recover any matrix from its corresponding tag ($\text{tag}(k)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, 120$) use the following OCTAVE code:

```
% Choose any k = 1, 2, ..., 120
% Change tag(k) string into an array
arr=(dec2base(tag(k),10)-'0')'; % arr is a 1x5 vector now
% Now get the matrix
for n=1:5,m(n,arr(n))=1;,end
% Print tag and matrix in compact format
reshape(sprintf("%i",[arr;m]),6,5)
```

The tables below collate results; in each box the tag is highlighted in yellow, directly above its corresponding matrix.

12345	12354	12435	12453	12534	12543	13245	13254	13425	13452
10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000
01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	00100	00100	00100	00100
00100	00100	00010	00010	00001	00001	01000	01000	00010	00010
00010	00001	00100	00001	00100	00010	00010	00001	01000	00001
00001	00010	00001	00100	00010	00100	00001	00010	00001	01000
13524	13542	14235	14253	14325	14352	14523	14532	15234	15243
10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000
00100	00100	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00001	00001
00001	00001	01000	01000	00100	00100	00001	00001	01000	01000
01000	00010	00100	00001	01000	00001	01000	00100	00100	00010
00010	01000	00001	00100	00001	01000	00100	01000	00010	00100
15324	15342	15423	15432	21345	21354	21435	21453	21534	21543
10000	10000	10000	10000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000
00001	00001	00001	00001	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000
00100	00100	00010	00010	00100	00100	00010	00010	00001	00001
01000	00010	01000	00100	00010	00001	00100	00001	00100	00010
00010	01000	00100	01000	00001	00010	00001	00100	00010	00100
23145	23154	23415	23451	23514	23541	24135	24153	24315	24351
01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000
00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00010	00010	00010	00010
10000	10000	00010	00010	00001	00001	10000	10000	00100	00100
00010	00001	10000	00001	10000	00010	00100	00001	10000	00001
00001	00010	00001	10000	00010	10000	00001	00100	00001	10000
24513	24531	25134	25143	25314	25341	25413	25431	31245	31254
01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	00100	00100
00010	00010	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	10000	10000
00001	00001	10000	10000	00100	00100	00010	00010	01000	01000
10000	00100	00100	00010	10000	00010	10000	00100	00010	00001
00100	10000	00010	00100	00010	10000	00100	10000	00001	00010
31425	31452	31524	31542	32145	32154	32415	32451	32514	32541
00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100
10000	10000	10000	10000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000
00010	00010	00001	00001	10000	10000	00010	00010	00001	00001
01000	00001	01000	00010	00010	00001	10000	00001	10000	00010
00001	01000	00010	01000	00001	00010	00001	10000	00010	10000

34125	34152	34215	34251	34512	34521	35124	35142	35214	35241
00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100
00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00001	00001	00001	00001
10000	10000	01000	01000	00001	00001	10000	10000	01000	01000
01000	00001	10000	00001	10000	01000	01000	00010	10000	00010
00001	01000	00001	10000	01000	10000	00010	01000	00010	10000
35412	35421	41235	41253	41325	41352	41523	41532	42135	42153
00100	00100	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010
00001	00001	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	01000	01000
00010	00010	01000	01000	00100	00100	00001	00001	10000	10000
10000	01000	00100	00001	01000	00001	01000	00100	00100	00001
01000	10000	00001	00100	00001	01000	00100	01000	00001	00100
42315	42351	42513	42531	43125	43152	43215	43251	43512	43521
00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010
01000	01000	01000	01000	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100	00100
00100	00100	00001	00001	10000	10000	01000	01000	00001	00001
10000	00001	10000	00100	01000	00001	10000	00001	10000	01000
00001	10000	00100	10000	00001	01000	00001	10000	01000	10000
45123	45132	45213	45231	45312	45321	51234	51243	51324	51342
00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00001	00001	00001	00001
00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	10000	10000	10000	10000
10000	10000	01000	01000	00100	00100	01000	01000	00100	00100
01000	00100	10000	00100	10000	01000	00100	00010	01000	00010
00100	01000	00100	10000	01000	10000	00010	00100	00010	01000
51423	51432	52134	52143	52314	52341	52413	52431	53124	53142
00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001
10000	10000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	01000	00100	00100
00010	00010	10000	10000	00100	00100	00010	00010	10000	10000
01000	00100	00100	00010	10000	00010	10000	00100	01000	00010
00100	01000	00010	00100	00010	10000	00100	10000	00010	01000
53214	53241	53412	53421	54123	54132	54213	54231	54312	54321
00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001	00001
00100	00100	00100	00100	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010	00010
01000	01000	00010	00010	10000	10000	01000	01000	00100	00100
10000	00010	10000	01000	01000	00100	10000	00100	10000	01000
00010	10000	01000	10000	00100	01000	00100	10000	01000	10000

Now, each of the 24 tags leading with '1' can be mated with its four circulants using the OCTAVE 'circshift' command to eventually generate all of S_5 ; thus an automated 'fill-the-gap' operation. In fact, the same procedure applied to the 24 fivesomes leading with any integer 2, 3, 4, or 5, will also yield S_5 . Below is a complete list using '1' as lead, highlighted in boldface yellow; the entries in each 5x5 array have been sorted.

12345	12354	12435	12453	12534	12543	13245	13254	13425	13452	13524	13542
23451	23541	24351	24531	25341	25431	24513	25413	25134	21345	24135	21354
34512	35412	35124	31245	34125	31254	32451	32541	34251	34521	35241	35421
45123	41235	43512	45312	41253	43125	45132	41325	42513	45213	41352	42135
51234	54123	51243	53124	53412	54312	51324	54132	51342	52134	52413	54213
14235	14253	14325	14352	14523	14532	15234	15243	15324	15342	15423	15432
23514	25314	25143	21435	23145	21453	23415	24315	24153	21534	23154	21543
35142	31425	32514	35214	31452	32145	34152	31524	32415	34215	31542	32154
42351	42531	43251	43521	45231	45321	41523	43152	41532	42153	42315	43215
51423	53142	51432	52143	52314	53214	52341	52431	53241	53421	54231	54321

When summed, the five matrices corresponding to the tags in each 5x5 array will of course add up to a matrix of all 1's, as they should; for example

$$\begin{pmatrix} 14352 \\ 21435 \\ 35214 \\ 43521 \\ 52143 \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 10000 \\ 00010 \\ 00001 \\ 00100 \\ 01000 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 01000 \\ 10000 \\ 00010 \\ 00100 \\ 00001 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 00100 \\ 00001 \\ 01000 \\ 10000 \\ 00010 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 00010 \\ 00100 \\ 00001 \\ 01000 \\ 10000 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 00001 \\ 01000 \\ 00010 \\ 10000 \\ 00100 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 11111 \\ 11111 \\ 11111 \\ 11111 \\ 11111 \end{pmatrix}$$

Circulant evolution can work to generate the elements of any symmetric group S_n , provided, of course, that a set of lead tags is known; but these can be obtained through column swaps on a few tags. For example, to generate the 24 lead tags above, the following operations do it; source tags are labeled by **S** in the heading and highlighted in yellow, some obviously doing double duty. Thus a hybrid method has emerged.

S	2↔3	2↔4	2↔5	3↔4	3↔5	4↔5
12345	13245	14325	15342	12435	12543	12354
S	2↔4	2↔5	3↔4	3↔5	4↔5	
13245	14235	15243	13425	13542	13254	
S	2↔5	3↔5	4↔5			
14325	15324	14523	14352			
S	2↔5	3↔5	4↔5			
12435	15432	12534	12453			
S	2↔5	3↔5	4↔5			
13425	15423	13524	13452			
S	2↔5	3↔5	4↔5			
14235	15234	14532	14253			

Reference

[1] A. Cusmariu, 'S₄ once over easy', 10.5281/zenodo.106138